

Relationship Between Maternal Periodontitis & Adverse Pregnancy Outcomes- An Ambispective Study

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Abstract

Introduction: Pregnancy is normally a healthy physiological process that sometimes has adverse outcomes including low birthweight (<2500 g) or very low birthweight (<1500 g), pre-term birth (<37 weeks or very pre-term <32 weeks), growth restriction (weight for gestational age), pre-eclampsia, miscarriage and/or still birth.

Aims & Objective: To correlate the association between periodontal diseases in post-partum mother as a prospective risk for preterm and / or low birth weight babies to assess maternal periodontal status among pregnant women to assess reduction in prevalence of preterm / or low birth babies after treatment of maternal periodontitis.

Materials & Methods: An ambispective study case control design is chosen by including 100 mothers, aged 18-35 years with in a period of 4 months prior delivery and 48 hours after the birth of their child in case and control group respectively.

Results: This study indicated a 4.66 fold increase in PTLBW in cases of periodontal infection with CPI score ≥ 3 in comparison to periodontal infection with CPI score < 3 . Other workers observed 4.5 to 7 fold increase in incidence of PTLBW in cases with CPI score ≥ 3 . The important observation made in this study was literacy of the mother plays a major role in causation of periodontal disease as well as to PTLBW.

Discussion: Preterm birth (PTB) and low birth weight (LBW) are the leading perinatal problems worldwide. Mothers who receive periodontal therapy during pregnancy would be better suited to decrease the chances of delivering a baby with PLBW.

Keywords: Preterm birth, Low term birth

Introduction

Pregnancy is generally a healthy physiological process that typically has adverse outcomes including low birthweight (<2500 g) or very low birthweight (<1500 g), pre-term birth (<37 weeks or very pre-term <32 weeks), growth restriction (weight for gestational age), pre-eclampsia (commonly defined as maternal hypertension and proteinuria after the 20th gestational week), miscarriage and/or still birth.¹ Pregnancy is a delicate condition leading to different physiological changes in body structure, because of an increased production of different hormones such as oestrogens, progesterone, gonadotropins, and relaxine.² During pregnancy, the changes in hormone levels promote an inflammatory response that increases the risk of developing gingivitis and periodontitis. Even with good plaque control, 50%-70% of all women will develop gingivitis during their pregnancy, commonly referred to as pregnancy gingivitis, due to the variations in hormone levels. Pregnancy gingivitis generally manifests during the second and eighth month of pregnancy and is considered a consequence of the increased levels of the hormones

progesterone and estrogen, which can effect small blood vessels of the gingiva, making it more permeable.^{3,4} Pregnancy periodontitis can be observed as early as in 2nd month of pregnancy and may become worse in 8th month of pregnancy.⁵ Preterm birth, defined as delivery before 37 completed weeks (< 259 days) whereas full term pregnancy is around 40 weeks.⁶ Low Birth Weight is defined depending on whether the weight of the baby is < 2,500 g.⁷ Preterm infants who are born with a low birth weight are termed preterm low birth weight (PTLBW).⁸ Periodontal disease contribute to premature delivery and low birth weight as a result of pathogenic micro-organisms, or indeed their microbial products, such as lipopolysaccharide (LPS), reaching the uterus via the bloodstream, inducing cytokine release in the decidua or the membranes, resulting in increased prostaglandin production or, indeed, uterine muscle contraction. Inflammatory mediators such as cytokines and prostaglandins, when produced in the periodontal tissues or in other systemic organs in response to LPS stimulation, may also pose a real threat to the fetoplacental unit and increase the risk of preterm delivery and low birth

weight.⁹ Infection is now considered one of the major causes of PTLBW deliveries, responsible for somewhere between 30% and 50% of all cases.¹⁰ Some reproducible factors associated with PTLBW are demographic factors such as, age, race, socio-economic status, marital status, and behavioural factors as smoking, substance abuse, poor nutrition, excessive physical activity are included. Apart from these medical risk factors which includes, pre-dating pregnancy, poor obstetric history, uterine or cervical malformations/myomas, and pregnancy complications such as multiple gestation, abnormalities in amniotic fluid volume, vaginal bleeding, fetal abnormalities, serious infection, and abdominal surgeries constitute and play a role in PTLBW.¹¹ The 1996 study by Offenbacher and colleagues suggested that maternal periodontal disease could lead to a seven-fold increased risk of delivering a preterm low birth weight (PTLBW) infant. These authors concluded that approximately 18% of PTLBW cases might be attributable to periodontal disease. Since then, researchers have investigated these possible associations for over a decade or more. Therefore it is important to understand the underlying biologic mechanisms for the relationship between periodontal disease and adverse pregnancy outcomes such as preterm birth and low birth weight to provide a rationale for therapeutic interventions and exploration of other methods that may be used as adjuncts to the standard treatment. his study was done to correlate the association between periodontal diseases in post-partum mother as a prospective risk for preterm and / or low birth weight babies to assess maternal periodontal status among pregnant women to assess reduction in prevalence of preterm/ or low birth babies after treatment of maternal periodontitis.¹²

Materials and Method

This multicentre study was conducted in the Department of Periodontology and Oral Implantology, Rajasthan Dental College & Hospital, Jaipur in association with Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Mahila Chikitsalya

Study Design

An ambispective study case control design is chosen by including 100 mothers, aged 18-35 years within a period of 4 months prior delivery and 48 hours after the birth of their child in case and control group respectively .

Patient Group

Two groups were prepared as
 50 post-partum mothers - Control Group (periodontal intervention group)
 50 pregnant mothers - Case Group (non periodontal intervention group)

Inclusion Criteria

- Pregnant mothers aged between 18-35 years.
- Pregnant and < 22 weeks gestation at time of SRP
- Willing to be randomized , to complete treatment protocols and provide consent
- 2 or more sites measuring ≤ 5 mm probing depths (PD) and periodontal attachment loss of 1-2 mm

- +20 teeth
- +18 years of pregnant women, uniparous or multiparous with no history or presence of systemic disease

Exclusion Criteria

- Patient with history of systemic disease such as cardiovascular disease or placental or uterine complications or any other medical problems that may affect the study outcome was excluded
- Currently undergoing periodontal treatment
- Chronic regimen of aspirin or non steroidal anti-inflammatory drug
- 5 or more teeth requiring extraction
- Rampant decay or any other oral condition that, in the clinician judgement, would place the patient at unacceptable risk if treatment was delayed
- Chronic use of medications that cause gingival enlargement such as phenytoin, cyclosporin – or calcium channel antagonist
- Prescribed or using chlorhexidine or other mouth rinses with known anti-plaque or anti-inflammatory effect

Study Protocol

- All mothers were thoroughly briefed about the nature of the study and an informed consent was obtained .
- All the information gathered were recorded in a pre-designed Performa (Annexure-B).
- Each mother included in control group in the study was interviewed directly at the bed side. Information was collected about her qualification, age, family income and details about her husband, education and occupation. Adverse habits such as smoking, smokless tobacco use, alcohol consumption were also recorded for smoking and tobacco chew/paste, the type and form in which it was consumed was also noted.
- The post partum data was obtained from medical file. Information on the outcome of the current pregnancy was gathered from mother's medical record. The birth weight of the infant was also noted from the available infant and maternal record. The history of ypertension was noted from gynaecologist record.
- Periodontal clinical examination was carried out within 48 hours after delivery. The periodontal status of the mother was assessed by using community periodontal index (CPI Score) and Gingival Index (LOE & Silness).
- Each mother included in case group in the study was interviewed at the OPD time.
- Periodontal clinical examination was carried 4 months prior delivery upto delivery. The periodontal status of the mother was assessed by using Gingival Index (LOE & Silness) Plaque Index

Indicators

Three indicators of periodontal disease were used for the assessment: gingival bleeding, calculus and periodontal pockets. statistical Analysis or statistical analysis of observations, Chi-square test was applied. Data was analyzed SPSS software version 22. The correlation between the mean values of all clinical parameter GI, PI and CPI with PTLBW and NBW was done by Karl Pearson coefficient test.

Results

The age group distribution of the mothers between 18-35 years in case and control group. The distribution pattern in age group 18 - 25 indicated 40 % mothers (20/50) in case group(n=50) and 56% mother (28/50) in control group (N=50) in the age group of 26 - 30 indicated 44% mothers (22/50) in case group and 40% mothers (20/50) in control group and in the age group of 31-35, 16% mothers (8/50) were in case group and 4% mothers (2/50) were in control group. In case group and control group the selection of mothers was age-matched.

AGE GROUP (in yrs)	CASE GROUP		CONTROL GROUP	
	No	%	No	%
18 - 25	20	40.00	28	56.00
26 - 30	22	44.00	20	40.00
31 - 35	8	16.00	2	4.00
TOTAL	50	100.00	50	100.00

Table No. 1 Distribution According To Age of Mother of Case & Control Group

Graph No. 1 Distribution According To Age of Mother of Case & Control Group

AGE GROUP	CASE GROUP	CONTROL GROUP
18-25	23.03 ± 0.89	23.33 ± 0.92
26-30	28.65 ± 0.87	27.44 ± 1.62
31-35	33.00 ± 1.51	32.00 ± 1.41
18-35	26.00 ± 4.34	26.79 ± 4.68

Table No. 2 Mean ± Sd Age of Mother of Case Group & Control Group

Graph No. 2 Mean Age of Mother of Case Group & Control Group

	CASE GROUP		CONTROL GROUP	
	No	%	No	%
PTLBW	18	36.00	3	6.00
NBW	32	64.00	47	94.00
TOTAL	50	100.00	50	100.00

Table No. 3 Distribution According To Number of PTLBW & NBW Baby of Case & Control Group

The table 3 describes the distribution of babies delivered according to birth weight in case and control group. Out of 50 babies delivered in case group (n=50), 36% babies (18/50) delivered were PTLBW and 64% babies (32/50) delivered were full term normal for gestation age. Whereas in control group 6% babies (3/50) were delivered with PTLBW and 94% babies (47/50) were delivered ad full term normal for gestation age. The statistical analysis indicated a significant correlation in both group (P<0.05, Significant on Chi-square test).

Graph No. 3 Distribution According To No. of PTLBW & NBW Baby of Case & Control Group

	Case Group	Control Group
PTLBW	2303 ± 137	2344 ± 109
NBW	3117 ± 337	3290 ± 280

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	"t- Value"	"p- Value"	Result
Case	50	2303	137	1.656	< 0.0001	HS
Control	50	2344	109			

Table No. 4 Mean ± Sd Birth Weight of Baby of Case & Control Group (in Grams)

Graph No. 4 Mean Birth Weight of Baby of Case & Control Group (in Grams)

AGE GROUP (YRS)	CASE GROUP			CONTROL GROUP		
	PTLBW	NBW	TOTAL	PTLBW	NBW	TOTAL
18 - 25	12 (24.00)	12 (24.00)	24 (48.00)	1 (2.00)	20 (40.00)	21 (42.00)
26 - 30	4 (8.00)	18 (36.00)	22 (44.00)	1 (2.00)	23 (46.00)	24 (48.00)
31 - 35	2 (4.00)	2 (4.00)	4 (8.00)	1 (2.00)	4 (8.00)	5 (10.00)
TOTAL	18 (36.00)	32 (64.00)	50 (100.00)	3 (6.00)	47 (94.00)	50 (100.00)

Table No. 5 Distribution According To Age Group of Mothers & Birth Weight of Baby of Case & Control Group

Table 5 describes the distribution of deliveries of PTLBW and full term normal delivery according to the age group of mothers in case and control group. In control group, the babies delivered PTLBW and full term normal for gestation age were 2% (1/50) and 40% (20/50) respectively in the age group of 18 - 25, 2% (1/50) and 46% (23/50) respectively in the age group of 26 - 30, and, 2% (1/50) and 8% (4/50) respectively in the age group of 31 - 35. The statistical analysis indicated a significant correlation in both groups (P < 0.05 on chi-square test)

Whereas in case group, the babies delivered PTLBW and full term normal for gestation age were 24% (12/50) and 24% (12/50) respectively in the age group of 18 - 25, 8% (4/50) and 36% (18/50) respectively in the age group of 26 - 30, and, 4% (2/50) and 4% (2/50) respectively in the age group of 31 - 35. The

statistical analysis indicated a significant correlation in both groups (P < 0.05 on chi-square test)

Graph No. 5 Distribution According To Age Group of Mother & Birth Weight of Baby of Case Group

Graph No. 6 Distribution According To Age Group of Mother & Birth Weight of Baby of Control Group

Education	Case Group		Control Group	
	No	%	No	%
Illiterate	29	58.00	12	24.00
Primary	3	6.00	2	4.00
Middle	2	4.00	3	6.00
High School	1	2.00	2	4.00
Higher Secondary	4	8.00	5	10.00
Graduate	10	20.00	24	48.00
Post Graduate	1	2.00	2	4.00
Total	50	100.00	50	100.00

Table No. 6 Distribution According To Educational Status of Mothers of Case & Control Group

Table 6 describes the educational status of mothers in case and control group. In case group (n=50), 58% mothers were illiterate and 20% mothers were graduate, whereas in control group (n=50), 24% mothers were illiterate and 48% mothers were graduate.

Graph No. 7 Distribution According To Educational Status of Mothers of Case & Control Group

Educational Status	PTLBW		NBW		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Illiterate	15	30.00	14	28.00	29	58.00
Primary	0	0.00	3	6.00	3	6.00
Middle	0	0.00	2	4.00	2	4.00
High School	0	0.00	1	2.00	1	2.00
Hr. Secondary	0	0.00	4	8.00	4	8.00
Graduate & above	3	6.00	8	16.00	11	22.00
Total	18	36.00	32	64.00	50	100.00

Table No. - 7 Distribution According To Educational Status of Mothers & Birth Weight of Baby of Case Group

Table 7 shows the distribution of mothers according to educational level and birth weight of baby in case group. Out of 50 mothers in case group, 29 mothers (58%) were illiterate and out of these 29 illiterate mothers, 15 mothers delivered PTLBW babies. The statistical analysis indicated a significant correlation in both groups ($P < 0.05$ on chi-square test).

Graph No. 8 Distribution According To Educational Status of Mothers & Birth Weight of Baby of Case Group

SES	Case Group			Control Group		
	PTLBW	NBW	TOTAL	PTLBW	NBW	TOTAL
I	1 (2.00)	4 (8.00)	5 (10.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
II	4 (8.00)	20 (40.00)	24 (48.00)	0 (0.00)	35 (70.00)	35 (70.00)
III	1 (2.00)	6 (12.00)	7 (14.00)	1 (2.00)	4 (8.00)	5 (10.00)
IV	11 (22.00)	2 (4.00)	13 (26.00)	2 (4.00)	7 (14.00)	9 (18.00)
V	1 (2.00)	0 (0.00)	1 (2.00)	0 (0.00)	1 (2.00)	1 (2.00)
Total	18 (36.00)	32 (64.00)	50 (100.00)	3 (6.00)	47 (94.00)	50 (100.00)

Table No. 8 Distribution According To Socio Economic Status (SES) of Mothers of case & Control Groups

Table 8 shows that out of 50 mothers in case group, 22% mothers (11/50) in SES IV (upper lower SE class), delivered PTLBW, whereas out of 50 mothers in control group, 4% mothers (2/50) delivered PTLBW in SES IV (upper lower SES class).

Statistical analysis indicated that there is definite correlation between PTLBW and SES in case group ($P < 0.05$ Significant) whereas it is not significant in control group ($P > 0.05$ Not significant).

Graph No. 9 Distribution According To Socio Economic Status (SES) of Mothers of Case & Control Groups

CPI Score	Baseline	After Delivery
CPI=1	0	43 (86%)
CPI=2	0	7 (14%)
CPI=3	50	0
TOTAL	50	50

Table No. 9 Variation in Community Periodontal Index (CPI Score) of Control Group

Graph No. 10 Variation in Community Periodontal Index (CPI Score) of Control Group

CPI Score	Case Group			Control Group		
	PTLBW	NBW	TOTAL	PTLBW	NBW	TOTAL
CPI Score=1	0	0	0	1	42	43
CPI Score=2	0	0	0	2	5	7
CPI Score=3	18	32	50	0	0	0
Total	18	32	50	3	47	50

Table No. 10 Distribution According To Community Periodontal Index (CPI Score) of Mothers & Birth Weight of Baby of Case & Control Group

Table 10 shows the distribution of mothers of case and control group according to CPI score and birth weight of baby. Out of 50 mothers in control group, 43 mothers (86%) were having gingivitis with CPI score 1. Out of these 43 mother, 1 mother (2%) delivered as PTLBW whereas 42 mothers (84%) delivered as full term normal for gestation age. Remaining 7 (14%) in control group were having gingivitis with CPI score 2. Out of these 7 mothers, 2 mothers (4%) delivered as PTLBW and 5 mothers (10%) delivered as full term normal for gestation age.

In case group, out of 50 mothers of case group (as per study protocol) all mothers (100%) were having periodontitis with CPI score 3. Out of these 50 mothers of case group, 18 mothers (36%) delivered as PTLBW whereas 32 mothers (64%) delivered as full term normal for gestation age.

Graph No. 11 Distribution According To CPI Score of Mother & Birth Weight of Baby of Case Group

Graph No. 12 Distribution According To Cpi Score of Mother & Birth Weight of Baby of Control Group

Risk Factor	Case Group			Control Group		
	PTLBW	NBW	TOTAL	PTLBW	NBW	TOTAL
Hypertension	4 (8.00)	12 (24.00)	16 (32.00)	0 (0.00)	2 (4.00)	2 (4.00)
Tobacco	6 (12.00)	6 (12.00)	12 (24.00)	0 (0.00)	3 (6.00)	3 (6.00)
Smoking	1 (2.00)	12 (24.00)	13 (26.00)	0 (0.00)	4 (8.00)	4 (8.00)
Alcohol	1 (2.00)	12 (24.00)	13 (26.00)	1 (2.00)	2 (4.00)	3 (6.00)

Table No. 11 Distribution According To Associated Risk Factors of Mothers & Birth Weight of Baby of Case & Control Group

Table 11 is showing the role of other risk factors viz. Hypertension, Tobacco, Smoking and Alcohol in causation of PTLBW in mothers of case and control group. In case group out of 50 mothers, it was observed that 4 mothers were hypertensive (8%) delivered PTLBW babies

GRAPH NO. 13 Distribution According To Associated Risk Factors of Mothers of Case & Control Group

Birth Weight	Case Group	Control Group
PTLBW	4 (8.00)	0 (0.00)
NBW	12 (24.00)	2 (4.00)
TOTAL	16 (32.00)	2 (4.00)

Table No. 12 Distribution According To Hypertension of Mother And Birth Weight of Baby of Case & Control Group

Table 12 shows the distribution of cases according to prevalence of hypertension in mothers in case and control group. Out of 50 mothers in case group, 16 mothers were having hypertension and out of these 4 mother delivered PTLBW babies and 12 mothers delivered as full term normal for gestation age. Whereas out of 50 mothers in control group, 2 mothers were having hypertension and both of them delivered full term normal for gestation age. Statistical correlation between HT of mother and PTLBW in both groups was non-significant ($P > 0.05$).

Graph No. 14 Distribution According To Hypertension of Mother & Birth Weight of Baby of Case & Control Group

Birth Weight	Case Group	Control Group
PTLBW	1 (2.00)	1 (2.00)
NBW	12 (24.00)	2 (4.00)
TOTAL	13 (26.00)	3 (6.00)

Table No. 13 Distribution According To Alcohol Intake Habit of Mother & Birth Weight of Baby of Case & Control Group

Table 13 shows the distribution of cases according to mother's history of alcohol intake and birth weight of baby. One case was reported from the mother of case group and one case was reported from the control group who delivered PTLBW. In this study, no correlation was observed between mother's alcohol intake and PTLBW in control group ($P > 0.05$).

Graph No. 16 Distribution According To Tobacco Chewing/Paste Habit of Mother & Birth Weight of baby of Case & Control Group

Graph No. 15 Distribution According To Alcohol Intake Habit of Mother & Birth Weight of Baby of Case & Control Group

Birth Weight	Case Group	Control Group
PTLBW	6 (12.00)	0 (0.00)
NBW	6 (12.00)	3 (4.00)
TOTAL	13 (26.00)	3 (6.00)

Table No. 14 Distribution According To Tobacco Chewing/Paste Habit of Mother & Birth Weight

Table 14 shows the distribution of cases according to habit of tobacco use in mother (tobacco chew/paste use) and birth weight of baby, in case and control group. Out of 50 mothers of case group, 12 mothers (24%) were using tobacco, whereas in control group, only 3 mothers (6%) were using tobacco. Further evaluation indicated that 12% mothers (6/50) delivered with PTLBW in case group ($P < 0.05$), whereas no case was reported from the control group ($P > 0.05$).

Birth Weight	Case Group	Control Group
PTLBW	1 (2.00)	0 (0.00)
NBW	12 (24.00)	4 (8.00)
TOTAL	13 (26.00)	4 (8.00)

Table No. 15 Distribution According To Smoking Habit of Mother & Birth Weight of Baby of Case & Control Group

Table 15 shows the distribution according to smoking habits of mothers and birth weight of case and control groups. In case group, out of 50 mothers, 13 mothers were smoker whereas in control group, out of 50 mothers there was 4 cases reported as smoker. Out of the 13 smoker mothers of case group only one mother delivered with PTLB and whereas in control group, no case delivered with PTLB.

Graph No. 17 Distribution According To Smoking Habit of Mother & Birth Weight of Baby of Case & Control Group

Discussion

Preterm birth (PTB) and low birth weight (LBW) are the leading perinatal problems worldwide and have evident public health implications, as they are closely related to perinatal mortality and morbidity.¹³

Multiple factors have been reported as a cause of PTB and/or LBW. Out of reported factors some are preventable e.g. alcohol, smoking or drug use during pregnancy, high or low maternal age, low socioeconomic status, maternal infection etc.

A coordinated effort between the oral health and prenatal communities can benefit maternal and child health outcomes. If on-going large and well-designed studies continue to support such results, current practice management for pregnant women will need to be reassessed. Such results should be carefully considered by dental providers, cautioning them not to reject treatment of periodontal diseases with routine prophylaxis and non-surgical periodontal therapy before the 35th week of pregnancy.

In spite of the fact that the child bearing age is from 15 to 45 years, the age group considered for the present study was 18 to 35 years. The rationale selecting the age group between 18 to 35 years is that the periodontal diseases are gram-negative anaerobic infections that can occur in women in the age group of 18 to 34 years. It has been further reported that women of child-bearing age and pregnant women have elevated levels of estrogen and progesterone, which makes them prone for periodontal disease.¹⁴

Age group distribution of mothers in case group and control group has indicated that most of deliveries took place in the age group of 18-30 years. The distribution pattern is almost equal in both control (96%) and case group (84%). Our results are in accordance with the results reported in the literature, which have reported about 80% of deliveries occurs before the age of 30 year.¹⁵

A positive correlation has been reported between mother's educational level and causation of periodontal disease.^{16,17} Literacy of mother is an important parameter for the fetal outcome. This finding is indicated that in case group most of the

mothers 29/50 (58%) were illiterate and out of these 29 illiterate mothers 15 (30%) delivered PTLBW babies ($P < 0.05$ on Chi-square test). This finding indicated that there is a significant association between education level of mothers and birth weight of baby. Our observations are in accordance with the reported observations by Garvey A, et al.¹⁸

Socio-economic distribution in studied population indicated that in both groups, the maximum number of mother were from SES II (upper middle SE class) but at the same time it was observed that PTLBW deliveries were more in SES IV in case group. This finding was further evaluated and it was observed that in spite of good Socio-economic Status IV in the case group (who delivered 11 (22%) PTLBWs) all of these mothers were illiterate. As reported that positive correlation exists between lower socio-economic status and periodontal disease leading to PTLBW.^{15,16} In this study illiteracy had been found to be more significant factor in comparison to SES as a cause of periodontal disease leading to PTLBW.

In this study, the babies delivered with PTLBW were 6 % (3/50) in the control group mothers with CPI score 1 or 2 which is comparable with the reported prevalence of 10% of PTLBW in India.^{19,20} whereas in the case group mother with CPI score 3, PTLBW was 36%, which is much higher than the reported in Indian situations ($p < 0.05$). With this observation it is clearly evident that periodontal disease with CPI score 1 and 2 did not contributed to adverse outcome of pregnancy but periodontitis with CPI score 3 have definite role in adverse outcome of pregnancy causing PTLBW babies.

It had reported that periodontal disease causes increased levels of biological fluids that induce labor. Previous research reported that periodontal infection causes a faster-than-normal increase in the levels of prostaglandin and tumor necrosis factor molecules that induce labor. When periodontal disease is present, the number of bacteria significantly increases by as much as 10,000 times the original population. It was further reported that immune system relaxes lightly during pregnancy so as not to harm the foetus and hence more bacteria grow when the immune system is not working in full throttle. The bleeding gums in periodontal disease gives the way to bacteria, who enters in the blood stream, travel through the mother's body, and enter the placenta causing poor fetal growth and as a result PTLBW baby.

Role of other risk factors as a cause of PTLBW was evaluated. The main factors which were evaluated were Hypertension, Tobacco, Smoking and Alcohol in both groups. In case group mothers, it was observed that use of tobacco (smokeless tobacco-chewing/ paste) in mothers is playing a major role (12%) in causation of PTLBW, whereas in control group it was not significant. In this study, no other factor was found to play a significant role in causing PTLBW in mothers of both the groups. The term 'smokeless tobacco' is used to describe tobacco that is consumed without heating or burning at the time of use. Smokeless tobacco can be used orally or nasally. The oral use of smokeless tobacco is widely prevalent in India; the different methods of consumption include chewing, sucking and applying tobacco preparations to the teeth and gums.²¹ Other studies also reported a high proportion of low birth weight babies in users of

smokeless tobacco.²² In this study the data indicated that there is no significant correlation between smoking and PTLBW ($P > 0.05$) as well as no significant correlation was observed between mother's alcohol intake and PTLBW in control group ($P > 0.05$).

As the CPI index selected under our study was restricted to score 1 to 3 and the CPI index of 4 or more were exclude. The CAL score expectedly shows the score of zero, rendering the relationship of our study as insignificant. Although CAL does not yield any data on the activity or the presence of periodontal

disease, it is the only value that can be compared with other studies, so we used it.

This study indicated a 4.66 fold increase in PTLBW in cases of periodontal infection with CPI score $3 \geq$ in comparison to periodontal infection with CPI score <3 . Other workers,^{23,24,25} observed 4.5 to 7 fold increase in incidence of PTLBW in cases with CPI score ≥ 3 . The important observation made in this study was literacy of the mother plays a major role in causation of periodontal disease as well as to PTLBW.

Fig. 1: Periodontal diseases associated with a wide array of systemic diseases & conditions

Fig. 2: Adverse Pregnancy Outcomes

Fig. 3: The role of fetus on beginning of labor

Fig. 4: Simplified Scheme of Some of The Putative Mechanism Involved in Preterm Rupture of the Membranes

Fig. 5: Proposed- Schematic Mechanism of Periodonto-pathogenic Bacteria to Incite Preterm Labour

Fig. 6: Proposed biological model of periodontal disease and pre-term low birth weight

Fig. 7: Armamentarium

Fig. 8: Digital baby weighing scale

Fig. 9: PTLBW Infant on weighing scale

Fig. 10: NBW Infant on weighing scale

Fig. 11: CPI Score

CPI score 1

CPI score 2

CPI score 3

Summary & Conclusion

Preterm birth (PTB) and low birth weight (LBW) are the leading perinatal problems worldwide. This problem is multifactorial and important since it is closely related to perinatal mortality and morbidity. Out of reported factors some are preventable e.g. alcohol, smoking or drug use during pregnancy, high or low maternal age etc. and some are non preventable e.g. intrauterine maternal infection etc. Recent studies indicated a significant correlation between periodontal infections in mother and PT/LBW babies hence this study was undertaken to establish a cause effect relationship between periodontal disease of mother and PTLBW babies.

In spite of the fact that the child bearing age is from 15 to 45 years, the age group considered for the present study was 18 - 35 years, as the periodontal diseases are gram-negative anaerobic infections are more common in the age group of 18 to 34 years.

In this study, in the control group with CPI score 1 or 2 the babies delivered with PTLBW were 6 %, which is comparable with the reported PTLBW prevalence of 10% in India. Whereas in the case group with CPI score 3, the babies delivered with PTLBW were 36%, which is much higher than the PTLBW reported in Indian situations ($p < 0.05$). These observations indicated that periodontal disease with CPI score 1 or 2 does not contribute to adverse outcome of pregnancy but periodontitis with CPI score 3 has definite role in adverse outcome of pregnancy causing PTLBW babies.

Most of deliveries took place in the age group of 18-30 years. The distribution pattern of deliveries is almost equal in both control (96%) and case group (84%). Literacy of mother indicated that in case group (periodontal disease with CPI Score= 3), most of the mothers were illiterate (58%) whereas in control group maximum numbers of mother were literate. A positively correlation of periodontal disease and lower education was also observed. In this study a significant positive correlation was also observed between level of education and birth weight of the baby in the group of cases.

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